

Origin Analysis of Overpressures and Quantitative Assessment in the Dongfang Area, Yinggehai Basin

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Abstract: Analysis of overpressure origins serves as the foundation for pressure prediction and hydrocarbon accumulation studies. Overpressure is widely distributed in the Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin, demonstrating a close yet complex relationship with hydrocarbon accumulation. It is imperative to conduct in-depth research on the origins of overpressure and perform quantitative evaluation. Analysis utilizing well log combinations, loading-unloading curves, and acoustic velocity-density crossplots was conducted to investigate the origins of overpressure in the Dongfang area, Yinggehai Basin. Research results indicate that two-stage overpressure is widely developed in the Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin. The first overpressure zone occurs in strata above the mid-lower Yinggehai Formation at 1000-1500m depth, with a pressure coefficient over 1.3; the second segment is located in the Huangliu Formation below 2400m, with a pressure coefficient exceeding 1.5. Acoustic time difference, density, and resistivity logging curves exhibit significant responses to overpressure, manifesting as reversals to varying degrees. Integrated analysis with multiple methods indicates that the overpressure in the Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin is primarily caused by a combination of hydrocarbon-generation pressurization and undercompaction. The magnitude of hydrocarbon-generated overpressure primarily ranges from 5 to 20 MPa, contributing 40% to 70% of the total overpressure.

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1. Introduction

The recognition of overpressure began in the late 18th century with the observed deviation of formation fluid pressure from hydrostatic conditions. Further studies have since confirmed that this phenomenon is widespread and intrinsically associated with the development of sedimentary basins. However, the origins of overpressure are multifaceted, usually resulting from a confluence of various mechanisms. The prevailing explanation throughout the 1990s attributed the generation of overpressure, and notably elevated overpressure levels, to undercompaction in sedimentary basins. [1-3]. The same era saw the proposal of several other hypothesized mechanisms, encompassing overpressure generation from hydrocarbon maturation, diagenetic reactions like the montmorillonite-to-illite transformation, fluid pressure transfer, and tectonic stresses. However, overpressure genesis is not singular; it frequently arises from a confluence of factors acting in concert within a basin [4-7]. Previous research has classified overpressure systems into two primary categories: self-sourcing and allochthonous overpressure [8,9]. Self-sourced overpressure is generated by internal processes within a geological system, without the involvement of external fluids. Key mechanisms include undercompaction [10,11], hydrocarbon generation [12,13], clay mineral transformation [14,15], and aquifer thermal expansion [16,17]. Allochthonous overpressure is caused by externally derived forces, such as

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changes in tectonic stress or hydrodynamic conditions. Typical mechanisms include tectonic compression and fluid pressure transfer from adjacent formations, such as tectonic stress [18,19] and fluid conduction overpressure [8, 20,21]. In the early stage, the Yinggehai Basin was simply considered to be dominated by overpressure caused by undercompaction [22]. As operations targeted deeper reservoirs, a significant challenge emerged: pore pressure forecasts based solely on undercompaction frequently contained large errors when verified against downhole data. Currently, the primary methods to identify the mechanism behind overpressure in a single-genesis stratum include the well logging curve combination method [2,23,24], effective stress method [25,26], acoustic-density crossplots method [27,28].

Eaton's and Bowers' methods are the primary quantitative techniques for overpressure evaluation and have been extensively used in field applications. Eaton's method is restricted to loading-type overpressure, whereas the unloading equation in Bowers' method is specifically designed for unloading-type scenarios. Neither is fit for evaluating composite-genesis overpressure. The method by Zhang et al. for quantifying overpressure contributions relies on an invariant acoustic velocity, an assumption often broken by unloading and hydrocarbon generation, resulting in underestimation [29]. Grounded in the principles of rock stress-strain behavior and pore architecture, Liu et al. constructed an operational model to evaluate overpressure generated by undercompaction and fluid expansion, demonstrating its utility in field studies [30].

Taking the Dongfang area of the central diapiric belt in the Yinggehai Basin as the research object, this study integrates existing exploration results and previous research findings. Based on detailed analysis of measured formation pressure, mud density, and logging data, it applies comprehensive methods such as well logging curve combination, loading-unloading curves, and acoustic velocity-density crossplots to investigate origins of overpressure in the Yinggehai Formation and Huangliu Formation. The study aims to clarify the abnormal high-pressure genesis mechanism, evaluate the contribution rate of single overpressure genesis, and thus provide certain guidance for overpressure research in hydrocarbon-bearing basins and petroleum exploration.

2. Geological Background

The Yinggehai Basin, situated at the junction of the Indosinian plate and Eurasian plate, is a Cenozoic high-temperature and high-pressure basin [31,32], with multiple fluid diapiric structures developed in central part, and contains abundant natural gas resources, as **Figure 1a** [33]. The basin hosts thick sedimentary layers rich in natural gas resources, ranking among the key areas for China's offshore oil and gas exploration and development. From the bottom upward, the Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin is developed with strata from the Paleogene Yacheng Formation, Lingshui Formation to the Neogene Sanya Formation, Meishan Formation, Huangliu Formation, Yinggehai Formation and the Quaternary Ledong Formation as **Figure 1b**. The sediment in the basin is mainly composed of fine-grained deposits. The lithology is dominated by thick successions of mudstone, with sandstones mostly being siltstone and fine sandstone. The formations such as the Meishan Formation, Huangliu Formation, and Yinggehai Formation developed in the basin have formed a good source-reservoir-cap assemblage [34]. The maximum reservoir pressure coefficient encountered in most areas of the basin is close to 2.3 [35].

Figure 1.(a) Location of the Dongfang Area in the Central Diapiric Belt of the Yinggehai Basin; (b) Comprehensive Stratigraphic Column.

3. Results

3.1. Overpressure Structural Characteristics

An integrated analysis of data from the Dongfang area, comprising formation pressure while drilling, mud density, and measured pressures from exploration wells, confirms the widespread presence of overpressure in the Yinggehai Basin. Vertically, the overpressure top interface in the study area is located within the Yinggehai Formation and Huangliu Formation, corresponding to depths of around 1100m and below 2500m, with pressure coefficients ranging from 1.0 to 2.1. The Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin exhibits two set of overpressure systems in the Figure 2. The first stage is mainly distributed in the strata above the middle-lower part of the Yinggehai Formation at a burial depth of 1000-1500 m. With increasing depth, the acoustic transit time and resistivity of mudstone remain basically constant or stable, while density increases linearly. The formation pressure reaches 10-20 MPa, pressure coefficient over 1.3. The second stage is primarily distributed in the Huangliu Formation at a burial depth of below 2.4 km. As depth increases, the acoustic transit time, density, and resistivity of mudstone deviate from the normal trend. The formation pressure reaches 40-70 MPa, pressure coefficient exceeding 1.5 (Figure 2a).

The overpressure top interface in the study area shallows with decreasing distance from the diapir. In the diapiric zone, the overpressure top interface of the Yinggehai Formation, as shown in wells D1 and D3 (Figure 2b), corresponds to depths of 900 m and 1050 m, respectively. In the non-diapiric zone, the overpressure top interface of the Yinggehai Formation, as indicated by well D4, is at a depth of 1.1 km. However, the overpressure in the Huangliu Formation is primarily developed in the diapiric zone, with corresponding depths generally below 2.2 km.

Figure 2. Pressure distribution with depth (a) and overpressure top interface distribution (b) in the Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin.

3.2. Origin of Overpressure

The process of abnormal pressure analysis involves two key steps: Identification, based on interpreting diagnostic well-log responses that reflect mechanism-specific changes in reservoir properties; and Discrimination, which utilizes methods from direct empirical techniques to indirect reasoning via integrated geological and experimental analysis [37-40]. Based on these methods, a comprehensive analysis is conducted using a synthesis of well-logging curves, loading-unloading diagnostics, and acoustic velocity-density crossplots to characterize the overpressure in the Dongfang area.

3.2.1. Combination analysis of logging curves

The intrinsic complexity of overpressure genesis, combined with the diverse factors influencing logging results, presents a significant challenge for accurate characterization. [36,39,41]. Given the complexity of overpressure genesis, its identification from logging data must rely on a comprehensive analysis combining multiple parameters. Therefore, a robust application of this method necessitates a dual consideration of logging responses: those sensitive to conductive properties (e.g., resistivity) and those sensitive to volumetric properties (e.g., acoustic, density) [42]. The combined interpretation of acoustic, resistivity, and density log data represents a minimum prerequisite for applying this method [2,23,36,43]: (1) disequilibrium compaction, if acoustic, resistivity, and density logs exhibit synchronous anomalies; (2) fluid expansion or pressure transfer, if anomalies are unsynchronized or density remains stable; (3) tectonic compression, if none of the curves show significant anomalies.

A characteristic feature of the overpressure in the Dongfang area is the asynchronous reversal observed in the well-logging curves. Specifically, the reversal depth of the density curve lags behind that of the acoustic transit time and resistivity curves. In well D1 (**Figure 3a**), the acoustic transit time reversal occurs at approximately 1.4 km, while the resistivity reversal is at 1.9 km. In well D3 (**Figure 3b**), within the depth range of 1.1-1.3 km, the acoustic transit time and resistivity reversals are at 1.1 km, but the density reversal is not obvious and shows a normal pressure trend. Based on this, it can be determined that the overpressure in the middle-lower part of the Yinggehai Formation and the Huangliu Formation in the Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin is not dominated by undercompaction, but should be attributed to fluid expansion or pressure transmission.

Figure 3. Pressure and electrical characteristics of (a) well D1 and (b) well D3.

3.2.2. Loading-unloading curve

Bowers defined the relationship between porosity and vertical effective stress--known as the Bowers chart or loading-unloading curve--as a diagnostic method for identifying overpressure origins [44]. Following its proposal, and especially since 2000, this technique has become a cornerstone in the field, with its successful application leading to widespread recognition [45]. Using the loading-unloading curve to further identify the overpressure genesis in the Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin, it is found that the overpressure points on the density-vertical effective stress and acoustic velocity-vertical effective stress (Figure 4) all deviate from the loading curve and fall on the unloading curve, indicating that there is unloading-induced overpressure in the Dongfang area.

Figure 4. Loading-unloading curve of the Dongfang area (a) crossplots of vertical effective stress vs. acoustic velocity (b) crossplots of vertical effective stress vs. density.

3.2.3. Acoustic velocity-density crossplots

Since the early 21st century, the acoustic velocity-density crossplots method for identifying overpressure genesis has seen growing adoption. On acoustic velocity-density crossplots, any overpressure not caused by disequilibrium compaction will deviate from the loading curve. The specific pattern and location of this deviation vary with the underlying genetic mechanism.: (1) Overpressure from fluid expansion or pressure transmission is identified by a slight acoustic velocity decrease and a stable or slightly decreasing density [46]; (2) Overpressure resulting from clay mineral transformation manifests as a stable or slightly decreasing acoustic velocity but an increasing density [47,48]; (3) Overpressure caused by load transfer or combined origins exhibits a clear acoustic velocity decrease accompanied by a density increase [37].

All overpressure points plotted on the acoustic velocity-density crossplots deviate downward from the loading curve, with the degree of deviation increasing with depth, and all fall within the overpressure zone of fluid expansion/pressure transmission and other non-disequilibrium compaction causes (Figure 5). Therefore, it is comprehensively determined that the overpressure in the Dongfang area of the Yinggehai Basin is dominated by fluid expansion/pressure transmission causes.

Figure 5. Acoustic velocity-density crossplots of the Dongfang area.

3.3. Quantitative Evaluation of Overpressure Genesis

Based on previous analysis, a method for evaluating overpressure contribution is proposed by fitting an exponential relationship between the acoustic velocity or density and vertical effective stress in normally pressured formations within the study area [49].

$$v = k * e^{c\rho} \tag{1}$$

$$\rho = k * e^{c\sigma} \tag{2}$$

in the above equation, v represents acoustic velocity, km/s; ρ denotes density, g/cm^3 ; k , c are constants; σ stands for effective stress, MPa.

Acoustic velocity, density, and resistivity typically increase with effective stress under normal pressure. Undercompaction delays this compaction trend, whereas fluid expansion overpressure causes a precipitous drop in effective stress, resulting in decreased velocity and resistivity but stable density.

The overpressure generated by any mechanism (e.g., fluid expansion, transmission, undercompaction) causes a decrease in effective stress, where the magnitude of the decrease is equal to the magnitude of the overpressure.

$$\Delta\sigma_1 = \ln(\rho/k) \cdot \frac{1}{c} - \Delta\sigma \tag{3}$$

$$G = \frac{\Delta\sigma_1}{\Delta\sigma} \cdot 100\% \tag{4}$$

in the above equation, $\Delta\sigma_1$ represents the overpressure increment, MPa; $\Delta\sigma$ denotes the corresponding total overpressure, MPa; G stands for the corresponding overpressure contribution rate, %.

Calculation results indicate that the overpressure from hydrocarbon generation primarily ranges between 5 MPa and 20 MPa, with its contribution accounting for 40%-70% (Table 1). The measured pressure points show a 45% contribution from hydrocarbon generation-induced overpressure, highlighting that overpressure from hydrocarbon generation is of critical importance for pressure prediction in hydrocarbon source rocks (Figure 6).

Figure 6. (a) Comparison of the measured snoic velocity and density calculated sound velocity. (b) Pressure prediction using snoic velocity and density calculated sound velocity in the Dongfang area.

Table 1. Contribution of hydrocarbon-generated to overpressure in Dongfang area.

Well	Depth(m)	Pressure (MPa)	Overpressure (MPa)	Hydrocarbon generation (MPa)	Contribution rate (%)
D1	920-1400	24.1	15.2	8.7	57.2
	>1950	48.4	33.5	19.7	58.8
D2	950-1400	18.5	9.7	4.7	48.5
	>2000	56.4	14.4	8.9	61.8
D3	1050-1350	21.4	11.2	5.8	51.2
L1	>2150	38.7	24.6	16.3	66.3

4. Conclusions

1) Two overpressure segments are widely developed in the Dongfang area. The first segment, with a pressure coefficient exceeding 1.3, lies above the mid-lower Yinggehai

Formation at 1-1.5 km depth. The second segment, with a pressure coefficient over 1.5, is located in the Huangliu Formation beneath 2.4 km. The overpressure distribution exhibits a characteristic of bulge-shaped uplift: the depth to the top of overpressure at the diapir core is relatively small, while that at the diapir margin increases.

2) Integrated geophysical analysis reveals the overpressure characteristics of the Dongfang area in the Yinggehai Basin: well-logging curves exhibit typical asynchronous reversals in acoustic interval time, resistivity, and density. Based on a comprehensive diagnosis using multiple methods such as composite well-log analysis, loading-unloading curves, and acoustic velocity–density crossplots, the overpressure in this area is determined to result from a combined origin of hydrocarbon generation and undercompaction. Quantitative evaluation indicates that hydrocarbon generation contributes an overpressure magnitude of approximately 5–20 MPa, accounting for 40% to 70% of the total overpressure.

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References

- Magara, K. Compaction and fluid migration, practical petroleum geology. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 1978.
- Fertl, W. H. Abnormal formation pressure: implication to exploration, drilling, and production of oil and gas resources. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 1976.
- Mann, D. M., Mackenzie, A. S. Prediction of pore fluid pressures in sedimentary basins. *Marine and Petroleum Geology*, 1990, 7(1), 55-65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0264-8172\(90\)90056-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0264-8172(90)90056-M)
- Barker, C. Calculated volume and pressure changes during the thermal cracking of oil to gas in reservoirs. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1990 74(8), 1254-1261. <https://doi.org/10.1306/0C9B247F-1710-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Osborne, M. J., Swarbrick, R. E. Mechanisms for generating overpressure in sedimentary basins: a reevaluation. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1997, 81(6), 1023-1041. <https://doi.org/10.1306/522B49C9-1727-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Swarbrick, R. E., Osborne, M. Mechanisms that generate abnormal pressures: an overview. *AAPG*, 1998, 70, 13-34. <https://doi.org/10.1306/M70615C2>
- Tingay, M. R. P., Hillis, R. R., Swarbrick, R. E., Morley, C. K., Damit, A. R., 2009. Origin of overpressure and pore-pressure prediction in the Baram Province, Brunei. *AAPG Bulletin*, 93(1), 51-74. <https://doi.org/10.1306/08080808016>
- Xie, X. N., Wang, Z. F., Li, S. T., et al. Characteristics of Overpressure Systems and Their Significance in Hydrocarbon Accumulation in the Yinggehai and Qiongdongnan Basins, China. *Acta Geologica Sinica*, 2003, 77(2), 285-266. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-6724.2003.tb00569.x>
- Xu, Z. X. Abnormal Formation Pressure and Its Relationship with Hydrocarbon Accumulation in the Xihu Sag. D. Chengdu: Chengdu University of Technology, 2015 .
- Dickinson, G. Geological Aspects of Abnormal Reservoir Pressures in Gulf Coast Louisiana. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1953, 37, 410-432. <https://doi.org/10.1306/5CEADC6B-16BB-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Hunt, J. M. Generation and Migration of Petroleum from Abnormally Pressured Fluid Compartments. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1990, 74(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1306/0C9B21EB-1710-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Barker, C. Aquathermal pressuring-role of temperature in development of abnormal-pressure zones. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1972, 56(10), 2068-2071. <https://doi.org/10.1306/819A41B0-16C5-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Law, B. E., Dickinson, W. W. Conceptual model for origin of abnormally pressured gas accumulations in low-permeability reservoirs. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1985, 69(8), 1295-1304. <https://doi.org/10.1306/AD462BD7-16F7-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Jowett, E. C., Cathles, L. Predicting Depths of Gypsum Dehydration in Evaporitic Sedimentary Basins. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1993, 77(3), 402-413. <https://doi.org/10.1306/BDF8C22-1718-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Powers, M. C. Fluid-Release Mechanisms in Compacting Marine Mudrocks and Their Importance in Oil Exploration. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1967, 51(7), 1240-1254. <https://doi.org/10.1306/5D25C137-16C1-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Daines, S. Aquathermal pressuring and geopressure evaluation. *AAPG Bulletin*, 1982, 88(1), 1153-1172. <https://doi.org/10.1306/03B5A35E-16D1-11D7-8645000102C1865D>
- Shi, Y. L., Wang, Y. C. Roll-back subduction and black-arc opening. *Acta Geologica Sinica*, 1993, 36(1), 37-43.
- Byerlee, J. D. Model for episodic flow of high-pressure water in fault zones before earthquakes. *Geology*, 1993, 21(4), 303-306. [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1993\)021<0303:MFEFOH>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1993)021<0303:MFEFOH>2.3.CO;2)

19. Yassir, N. A., Bell, J. S. Abnormally high fluid pressures and associated porosities and stress regimes in sedimentary basins. *SPE Formation Evaluation*, 1996, 11(01), 5-10. <https://doi.org/10.2118/28139-PA>
20. Yardley, G. S., Swarbrick, R. E. Lateral transfer: A source of additional overpressure? *Marine and Petroleum Geology*, 2000, 17(4), 523-537. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0264-8172\(00\)00007-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0264-8172(00)00007-6)
21. Deming, D., Cranganu, C., Lee, Y. Self-sealing in sedimentary basins. *Journal of Geophysical Research Atmospheres*, 2002, 107, 12-20. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001JB000504>
22. Zhang, Q. M., Dong, W. L. Overpressure system of hydrocarbon-bearing basins in China. *Acta Petrolei Sinica*, 2000, 21(6), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.7623/syxb200006001>
23. Fertl, W. H., Timko, D. H. How downhole temperature, pressure affect drilling. Part 3: overpressure detection from wireline methods. *World Oil*, 1972, 8, 36-66.
24. Wang, Z. L., Sun, M. L., Geng, P., et al. The development features and formation mechanisms of abnormal high formation pressure in southern Junggar region. *Petroleum Exploration and Development*, 2003, 30(1), 32-34. <https://doi.org/10.3321/j.issn:1000-0747.2003.01.008>
25. Bowers, G. L. Pore pressure estimation from velocity data: accounting for overpressure mechanisms besides undercompaction. *SPE Drilling & Completion*, 1995, 10(02), 89-95. <https://doi.org/10.2118/27488-PA>
26. Guo, X. W., He, S., Liu, K. Y., et al. Oil generation as the dominant overpressure mechanism in the Cenozoic Dongying depression, Bohai Bay Basin, China. *AAPG Bulletin*, 2010, 94(12), 1859-1881. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1673-5005.2022.06.016>
27. Tingay, M. R. P., Morley, C. K., Laird, A., et al. Evidence for overpressure generation by kerogen-to-gas maturation in the northern Malay Basin. *AAPG Bulletin*, 2013, 97(4), 639-672. <https://doi.org/10.1306/09041212032>
28. Dasgupta, S., Chatterjee, R., Mohanty, S. P. Magnitude, mechanisms, and prediction of abnormal pore pressure using well data in the Krishna-Godavari Basin, east coast of India. *AAPG Bulletin*, 2016, 100(12), 1833-1855. <https://doi.org/10.1306/05131615170>
29. Zhang, F. Q., Wang, Z. L., Zhong, H. L., et al. Recognition model and contribution evaluation of main overpressure formation mechanisms in sedimentary basins. *Natural Gas Geoscience*, 2013, 24(6), 1151-1158. http://dx.doi.org/10.9774/GLEAF.978-1-909493-38-4_2
30. Liu, T., Liu, J. D. Quantitative evaluation on overpressure generated from undercompaction and fluid expansion. *Acta Petrolei Sinica*, 2018, 39(9), 971-979. <https://doi.org/10.7623/syxb201809002>
31. Tang, X. Tectonic pattern of the South China Sea plate and its causes. *Petroleum Exploration and Development*, 1982, (1), 1-15 .
32. Li, S. T., Lin, C. S., Zhang, Q. M., et al. Episodic rifting of continental marginal basins and tectonic events since 10 Ma in the South China Sea. *Chinese Science Bulletin*, 1999, 44(1), 10-23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03182877>
33. Wan, Z. F., Xia, B., Xu, L. F., et al. Study on the dynamic mechanism of tectonic evolution in Yinggehai Basin. *Marine Science Bulletin*, 2010, 29(6), 654-657. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1001-6392.2010.06.010>
34. Zhang, H. L., Pei, J. X., Zhang, Y. Z., et al. Characteristics of overpressure reservoirs in the middle-deep Huangliu Formation, Eastern Area of the Yinggehai Basin. *Petroleum Exploration and Development*, 2013, 40(03), 284-293. <https://doi.org/10.11698/PED.2013.03.04>
35. Xiong, X. F., Xu, X. D., Gan, J., et al. Characteristics of differential distribution and migration-accumulation-reservoir of natural gas in the Central Diapir Belt, Yinggehai Basin. *Marine Geology Frontiers*, 2017, 33(07), 24-31. <https://doi.org/10.16028/j.1009-2722.2017.07003>
36. Zhao, J. Z., Li, J., Xu, Z. Y. Advances in the origin of overpressures in sedimentary basins. *Acta Petrolei Sinica*, 2017, 38(9), 973-998. <https://doi.org/10.7623/syxb201709001>
37. Han, X. J., Fan, C. Y., Gao, C., et al. Restoration method of disequilibrium compaction overpressure in tectonically uplifted area: A case study of Yanchang Formation in Xiasiwan area, Ordos Basin. *Natural Gas Geoscience*, 2023, 34(7), 1163-1172. <https://doi.org/10.11764/j.issn.1672-1926.2023.02.008>
38. Lu, X. S., Zhao, M. J., Zhang, F. Q., et al. Characteristics, origin and controlling effects on hydrocarbon accumulation of overpressure in foreland thrust belt of southern margin of Junggar Basin, NW China. *Petroleum Exploration and Development*, 2022, 49(5), 859-870. <https://doi.org/10.11698/PED.20220103>
39. Ai, N. P., Song, P., Li, W., et al. Genetic mechanisms and prediction of the deep abnormal high pressure in the Ledong area, Yinggehai Basin. *Geophysical and Geochemical Exploration*, 2023, 47(1), 190-198. <https://doi.org/10.11720/wtyht.2023.1007>
40. Ning, W. K., Ju, W., Xiang, R. Pressure prediction and genetic analysis of Huangliu Formation reservoir in DF block of Yinghai Basin based on neural networks. *Petroleum Geology & Experiment*, 2024, 46(5), 1088-1097. <https://doi.org/10.11781/sydz2024051088>
41. Ye, Z., Fan, H. H., Cai, J., et al. Investigation and application of a discrimination method for abnormal high formation pressure forming mechanism. *Journal of China University of Petroleum*, 2012, 36(03), 102-107. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1673-5005.2012.03.017>
42. Yu, J. Q., Sun, X. P., Yu, Y. C., et al. Research progress on deep formation pressure prediction technology. *Marine Origin Petroleum Geology*, 2024, 29(04), 337-347. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1672-9854.2024.04.001>
43. Bowers, G. L. Detecting high overpressure. *Leading Edge*, 2002, 21(2), 174-177. <https://doi.org/10.1190/1.1452608>
44. Bowers, G. L. Determining an Appropriate Pore-Pressure Estimation Strategy. *C. Offshore Technology Conference*, 2001, 13042. <https://doi.org/10.1190/1.1452608>

45. Hoesni, J. Origins of overpressure in the Malay Basin and its influence on petroleum systems. D. Durham, United Kingdom: University of Durham, 2004. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1876-3804\(20\)60088-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1876-3804(20)60088-X)
46. Conner, S., Swarbrick, R., Lahann R. Geologically-driven pore fluid pressure models and their implications for petroleum exploration: Introduction to thematic set. *Geofluids*, 2011, 11(4), 343-348. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-8123.2011.00354.x>
47. Lahann, R. W., Swarbrick, R. E. Overpressure generation by load transfer following shale framework weakening due to smectite diagenesis. *Geofluids*, 2011, 11(4), 362-375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-8123.2011.00350.x>
48. Zhang, J. C. Pore pressure prediction from well logs: methods, modifications, and new approaches. *Earth-Sci. Rev*, 2011, 108(1-2), 50-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2011.06.001>
49. Zhang, F., Wang, Z. L., Zhao, X. J., et al. Genetic mechanism of overpressure and its relationship with hydrocarbon accumulation in Dina-2 gasfield, Kuqa depression. *Acta Petrolei Sinica*, 2012, 33(5), 739-747. <https://doi.org/10.7623/syxb201205002>

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